

IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Almamatova Manzura Shavkatovna

Doctoral student of Gulistan State University

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Abstract: The article talks about the types of new pedagogical methods in the teaching of English language and the methods of its application in the lesson, as well as the practical importance of effective loading of the methods. Information is also given about how these methods contribute to the students' thorough mastery of a foreign language and their ability to speak that language.

Key words: method, English language, efficiency, education, student, foreign language ICT.

We know that this year, at the meeting of the video selector dedicated to Shavkat Mirziyoyev, under the chairmanship of our president Mirziyoyev, it was ensured that language teachers will be required to have a national and international certificate from 2021. This puts a huge responsibility on the shoulders of our foreign language teachers. Now, instead of traditional teaching methods, we need to organize the teaching process based on interactive methods, using new ICT. This education is a requirement of the times, and the teacher has to work on himself even more.

While paying attention to new methods of teaching in the article, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the type and effectiveness of these methods. New methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). According to it, textbooks are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language has also increased day by day. The science of a foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. The fact that some teachers do not know how to apply and do not use technologies during English lessons leads to some boredom of students.

It is for this reason, that is, in order not to extinguish the enthusiasm of the learner, the use of technologies and at least the computer during the lesson ensures that the learner's interest increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective. On the contrary, if we teachers do not choose

educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast video films, songs or texts containing complex words to elementary school students or show them through multimedia and computers, then When we show educational materials consisting of very simple texts to the students of rta and higher classes or groups, the students' interest in learning the language gradually fades and they do not master the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to a decrease in grades, a loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students.

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; — it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools ensures that the process of learning a foreign language is more interesting and effective for students. Therefore, it follows that during the lesson, it is not only useful to use technologies, but also to be able to use them in their place and use technologies. The main task is to ensure that it serves to increase the student's knowledge. According to the requirements of the current CEFR, i.e. the International European Education Standards, four competences: (writing, reading, listening, speaking) are conducted in English. it is important to use technologies effectively and appropriately during classes. For example, listening comprehension lessons have their own rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material he is listening to and to be able to analyze it without difficulty. For this, first of all, it is necessary to prepare the environment for playing the audio material, in which the listeners should ensure a calm environment, and the teacher should pay attention to the quality of the audio being played and the sound amplifiers working well, and the exercises to be performed before and after the audio is played. it should be ready and students should be provided with handouts.

In the course of foreign language lessons, it is necessary to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools. One such method is the use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson. Role-playing games are the application of different situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This method helps to create a language environment during the lesson. For example: in case 1, old friends meet by chance. Case 2: A child who does not follow the rules of the road

while crossing the road, that is, crosses the road where there is no crossing. Case 3. A customer enters the store to buy food. 4 Scenes of these situations are performed. Such life-like role-playing games create a language environment in the course of the lesson, and give students the opportunity to express their thoughts freely. In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to express their emotional states freely in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role-playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes. Making a mistake and correcting it also helps to learn the language and teaches students to pronounce correctly. The use of role-playing games during the lesson ensures that all students are actively involved in the lesson at the same time. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign language and create a lively, cheerful atmosphere in the classroom. This serves to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons. The next method is "Case-study" in English ("case" - specific situation, event, "study" - to study, analyze), a method aimed at carrying out teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations. is considered One of the most interesting methods is to divide into 3 groups in the game "Pantomimo". One person from each group is put on the board. They are given different words based on the list.

They have to explain the words to the rest of the group through gestures and actions without saying a word. To apply this method of "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read and the end of the story is referred to the judgment of the students; - "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles; - "Quick answers" helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson; - "Chigil yazdi" ("Warm-up exercises") using various games in the classroom to make students interested in learning [3]; - "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired; - "A chain story" method helps students to develop oral speech; - "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with students; - "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people; - The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the

topic; - Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time. As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process is envisaged.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies. possible

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